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A Revision of the Constitution, the Legal Justification for the Restriction

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Abstract:

Since the Constitution is part of the rules of substantive law in the process, you should have a look for it. Among the questions that arise in this regard and the research has addressed whether a constitution can be amended and revised if this means that a constitution should be drafted in a flexible constitution or otherwise? As the research has to say whatever is rigid constitution and less likely to change more can respect the rights of the public. The study reviewed and inferior types of corrupt practices and conduct is legal.

Keywords: Constitution, Legal Justification

Introduction:

Constitution, if not permanent, at least I need to lay the framework for a long period of their strength and ability to meet performance and future changes that are likely to be at the same time as the and the ambiguous and doubtful and suspicious leave. However, the revision and reform the way predict. Possible changes to the next round and conditions do not block important developments well it is completed, including the Constitution guarantees the right to revise ways since all laws for the peace and tranquility, security and prosperity of the nation and promoting the development of human and maintain the state of the country and urged the public interest or the majority of people tend to be the main condition for the modification of the Constitution. Personal desires groups with the aim of achieving power, noise, and temporary crisis, the usual ups and downs, which unfortunately is widespread in developing countries and not a pretext for the invasion of the Constitution, as amended, and the change is effective. Problems in the country and society in line with the Constitution and the adoption of laws and policies need to be resolved neither the Constitution of stop motion employee not robust constitution and regulations required by the society within which it can be and with every breeze is needed to modify the base is defective.

The 1358 Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Iran to reconsider the Assembly of experts (the constitutional) did not vote The indifference, the novice, the revolutionary act, condition resulting from a lack of overall

system overcoming the three branches of the leader as an observer, and fear of the return of the former regime forces, due to legal reasons mechanisms remain blacked out the review The first section is fully subject to review and revision of all types will be discussed.

The only word in the Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Iran in 1358 was clause contained in Article 132 of the said while the duties of president of the Provisional Council presidency ... Not be necessary to revise the Constitution However, this statement could not unravel the revision of the Constitution. In the second part of this thesis is presented in detail.

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Chapter I: General inquiry

Statement of Problem

Rights as a binding set of rules governing the provision of social relations, maintaining and improving the security and order or justice considers its purpose, the social context of development, the function of the process of change and transformation. In other words, although the principles are fixed, stable and unchanged (from natural or human nature) whose columns constitute legal order, however, the detailed rules for the regulation of social affairs and relations efforts in human population recruited obey the principle of relativity and according to the place and time of their diversity.

To express, "the rights of the rights to the words of life and as life changes, the rules have changed and the progress of life."

The result is that, contrary to the rules of science, humanities and social sciences as their main subject of the man and his behavior, Tailored to the circumstances of time and place of the rule. In other words, social norms (social norms) are the source of natural laws. Community law cannot be oblivious to these rules. The social rules by holding events and developments in social relations, of progress, evolution and all of the legal norms and legal systems are created. However, the schools of law, formal sources of law merely note and the recognition of the true shape change and the end of the effective period of this legislation is addressed.

Affect law is the only legal norms can be considered valid and eligible work the reliability of a source of law recognized by the legislature created.

Type of research:

This research aims to reflect the revision of the constitution is written.

Research objectives:

The main objective

1. The main objective of this study was to review the process of drafting the constitution.
2. Reload the one hand, and explain why and how the rights of the other party **secondary objective are:**

Typology review of the development process and the constitution

Authenticity of the legal review

Background Research:

This is important because in the process of codification is among the topics of the work but in this study, according to a comparative look at the world as it has been reviewed.

Research questions:

1. Does a change have in the constitution review process in Iran?
2. What type of constitution, according to its uses and what types of revision?

Hypothesis:

1. Looks at changes in the constitution review process were to have more of this Act.
2. It appears that the constitution of a flexible constitution, as expressed in this type of result is not good.

The research method:

The method has been used to explain the writing and research methods and libraries that address the various sources including research and development of its review was escorting.

Research domain:

Scope of this research is in the public law and the constitution.

Chapter II: Concepts

In this case, it is critically important forms and formalities nor the content and intent or purpose. Formalities or approved by the competent authority is the source of authority for rules in other words, is the law contains a "fundamental rule of recognition".

Which has been accepted by the authorities? This rule defines certain sources as sources of law. Basal stems from one source, the rule of "authentic" is regardless of whether just or unjust. While this is the only case of such norms are formed in social relations that legislator has identified and formulation and they have been without a Creator how to identify the norms and rules of the transition from "social" to the "right" order which is subject to the "rules of recognition" is mentioned.

The international legal system that obeys the principle of unity of the state and the citizens almost is the revision of the rules in various ways conventions or norms of unwritten rules, cumulative and collective manner.

In the first draft of the pen was not approved and removed. However, since the social dynamics of an uncontrollable and ignore (and this is subject to revision and correction is inevitable) , after more than ten years of life, the new government of the need to change some of the samples were crystallized law.

First topic: the concept of constitutional review of the literature of public law

The theoretical introduction to the topic, based on literature review of constitutional law will be discussed.

In order to investigate the conceptual review of a variety of species, many aspects of the legal entity will be explored. No processing of practical and objective review of the legal order refer to the status of the case and the fact that different systems and extraction systems, although brief reflection on theory revision is necessary. A revision of the theory, in different ways forward that may address some of the ways would be useful to review our constitution.

First Speech: The same concepts and ways of carrying out a review of the depth and breadth

With respect to legal literature, several words in the text of the constitution is changed.

However, there appears to be little difference in the meaning of these concepts persists in the legal system there. But formulated (at least theoretically) in this context, it can be reviewed in terms of depth and breadth that is also considered. Depth review of its function and impact on the life of existing law is constitutional; it will have three main forms:

- Accession means the addition of principle or principles of the Constitution in that it did not exist before.
- Remove all of life as a rule of constitutional law so that the text of the Constitution out.
- Modify to change the meaning of the concepts and components of a rule of constitutional

Its main strength is such that it remains whether this regulatory approach is modified (modified reduction) or an increase or a combination of these elements and concepts (Modified Promotion).

The second statement: revised terms of the ability to change the Constitution:

Full or partial revision according to most constitutions, it seems reviewed by creating a new constitution is different.

Basically, the goal of enhancing and supporting the rule of constitutional review of the political community and when it comes to the existing provisions of law, In particular the developments of the political community is

not covered by the Act, adaptability and efficiency. After the revision, the cases of improper modification or deletion of accession, it is appropriate and proportionate thought without complete removal of the constitution and the establishment of a new constitution emerged however, some basic rules, including flexible and rigid separated from each other are two types of review:

Inconspicuous revisions and thoroughly the second problem:

The harvest on the acceptability and desirability Revision of the Constitution in terms of constitutional law, "any fraction of incorporation or change one or more of the Constitution, revised and say how often and how the revision of the Constitution." However, legal scholars may not agree to accept such an institution and certain doctrine has been in this area.

Chapter III: A Reflection on the revision of the Constitution and the constraints facing the constitution as the fundamental law, the elements of governance and ensure the rights of the people and must undergo a whirlwind of political events and are subject to volatility and uncertainty to be revered the break.

On the other hand, one should not forget that the law in relation to the political and administrative life of the people. The development and evolution of various social, economic and political conditions, relationships and proposes new threads which requires the development of appropriate laws and progress. On the other hand, the ease of review and change the constitution because this is worrying which caused a rise in insecurity and political institutions of the country will be permanently legislation that is likely to change at any time at the mercy of the authorities cannot be regarded as a fundamental law.

Initiative, in retrospect, a very important point is that usually the strongest position of a country or entity is:

1. The executive branch of government in which absolute power is allocated to the right, whether or not in the Constitution.

The classic authoritarian regimes and even some contemporary constitutional regimes initiative Constitutional authority is governed by:

According to Article 27 of the Constitution of Morocco, revise the constitution of rights.

2. This right belongs to the people's democratic regimes:

Pursuant to Articles 118 to 123 of the Constitution of the Swiss initiative to revise the proposal to approve, by the people and the federal parliament.

Pursuant to Article 5 of the United States Constitution, Legislatures of two thirds majority of the members of the Constitution is revised.

3. In some countries between the executive and legislative authority to revise divided according to Article 89 of the Constitution of France's initiative to revise the Constitution, jointly owned by the president and parliament.

The second problem: the constraints imposed on the revision in addition to the revision of the Constitution inflexibility heavy may be specific reasons for resorting to revise avoided.

Some of the limitations are as follows:

The first speech limitations topic is constitution the of country's political system and the political and legal document of the country.

Internal changes in the system, so that the cylinder does not alter the system, seems to be normal; But if the elements of the system (such as the form of government, the dominant social values, unity and territorial integrity, etc.) created uncertainty or changes arise, the system will be doomed to collapse. The revised constitution relating to the establishment of many countries is prohibited:

- The following Article 89 of the Constitution of France, the government of the Republic cannot be revised.
- The part of Article 5 of the United States Constitution, the principle of equal representation of states (each state has two members) in the Senate is not revisable.
- Article 79 of the Federal Constitution of 1949, the federal government removed the structure is strictly forbidden, consequently, the review in this case is not acceptable.
- According to Article 100 of the Constitution of 1970 in Morocco, subject to the provisions of the monarchy and religion cannot be reviewed or changed.

The second speech limitations due to the circumstances and time limits for example, if the country is occupied by foreigners or the territorial integrity of the country are in danger, Circumstances may be considered appropriate to revise and amend the Constitution.

According to Article 89 of the Constitution of France, if the entire country is at risk and risk the possibility of any review and there is no change in the constitution may be provided in the Constitution which at any given time does not revise the constitution. This does not be because of a substantial revision of the Constitution and the advantages and disadvantages are well known.

French Constitution of 1791, amending the Constitution before the legislative period (four years) was banned. It does not seem reasonable time limit specified in the Constitution; it may require changes in the regulatory change.

This is because usually the time to review the restrictive provisions of the constitutions of countries cannot be predicted. It can be revised Under Article 118 of the Constitution of Switzerland at any time, in whole or in part.

Conclusion:

As mobility and variability of relative stability, the rule of law is indisputable description but in accordance with the rules of the social requirement. Legal rules as the rules of society must change in proportion to changes in social relations and phenomena are accepted and accommodated.

Law rules in the context of sociological and psychological logic governing the conduct of members of the human (as manufacturers and subject to the rules) as opposed to irrational institutional review shows.

Publicly or revise the secrecy of the "explicit or implicit", from the depth and breadth of the impact of the quality of the "Promotion adjustment or modification, deletion or accession" and demonstrates the depth and breadth of the quantitative impact of the "full or partial review divided.

Ease or difficulty of revising the Constitution as well as hard or flexible, depending and legal authorities to review the "legislature, congress or a joint meeting of the houses of parliament, specifically institution" independently or in conjunction with their constitutional referendum.

In some rare cases, such as the California Constitution (electoral board) were permitted to directly review the constitution.

Although in most cases, the revision of the constitution of Parliament as an institution (Sometimes with the laws and regulations governing the procedures and regulations sometimes specific) is used but there is no rule of law and legal institutions that specific type of this tract is preferred.

However, in light of the prevailing attitude of the democratic development of public law, relationship with the public authorities, as the owners of the governance review and final determination of the content of the Constitution whether on stage or in modified form, not only should not be overlooked but all the steps involved in this process and its regulations governing the democratic spirit (non-essential) to give full consideration.

Accordingly, the proposed revision to the approved final ducts should be made public so that the public will be the priority. Adopting this approach enables the principle of the sovereignty of the people and institutions will emerge from democratic style revision of the Constitution to be used as a reference.

However, the necessity of maintaining the stability and strength of the Constitution lies in the excellent political and legal order of the regulations require that a revision of the constitution by a democratic legislature, differently from ordinary laws are enacted and amended and in particular to strengthen democracy (and the reduction of non-democratic trachea harvest of legislative assemblies in terms they oversee public heed not their members), the constitutional referendum as a condition of "adequate" by the review boards should be used.

Regardless of any benefit and advantage of flexible and may be unwritten constitution and any weakness in the constitution and may be inflexible, in fact, the current tendency of the modern world is actually the constitution and inflexible. Currently all countries have this kind of constitution the only example of the unwritten constitution, flexible constitution of England and probably the first and last of these will remain Constitution. The United States is the first country to create a constitution and inflexible. Other countries imitated the American experience.

France is the second country that constitution was created. It seems that the future constitution is inflexible.

There are several reasons for this opinion:

The first reason is that in the modern world today is the tendency to the constitution the fundamental rights of the individual against the power of the state guarantee the aim is to provide a rigid constitution.

The second reason is that the current democratic system is ideal nations that his destiny to rule and so far as it is possible to restrain the executive branch to be converted into a giant dictator.

This objective is achieved by a constitution should be inflexible. Finally, the fourth reason is that in today's world many countries are managed by the federal government system and the federal government does not need a constitution and inflexible.

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